
TEACHERS' SUPPORT SERVICES AS PREDICTORS OF THEIR JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study examined teachers' support services as predictors of their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study was a correlational research design. The population of the study is 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six Education Zones in Anambra State. The sample of 660 teachers (that is, 10% of teachers' population) was used for the study. Multistage sampling techniques comprising of proportionate stratified and simple random sampling technique was used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection: Teachers' Support Services Questionnaire (TSSQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ). Face validation was done by three experts while construct validation was carried out with Principal Component Analysis approach. The reliability of the instruments was pilot tested in Enugu State using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient and the average coefficient values of 0.82 for TSSQ and 0.87 for TJCQ are considered highly reliable and suitable for the study. Simple regression analysis was used for the study. The study revealed that work environment ($r=0.651$ $p=0.000$), in-service training ($r=0.578$ $p=0.000$) and teamwork ($r=0.567$ $p=0.000$) positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that provision of teachers' support services positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that, for effective teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State, the state government in collaboration with State education board should continually provide teachers with good support services such that could be so motivating to sustain and increase teachers' work morale efficiency.

Keywords: Teacher's support services, job commitment, work environment, in-services training, teamwork.

Introduction

Teachers' job commitment is defined as the strength of a teacher's identification and involvement with the teaching job. It determines whether a person will leave or remain in the teaching profession or not. Kaegon and Okere (2023) defined teachers' job commitment as a psychological state that characterizes a teacher's relationship with his or her profession, and has implications for the decision to remain involved with it. It is the emotional bond between the teacher and the school. Teachers' job commitment is regarded as a power or quality needed to approach stress and change. It includes factors such as honesty, responsibility, and tolerance for fallibility. Teachers' job commitment is of importance as it is associated with greater job effort and involvement, that is, committed employees are less likely to leave their position and display other withdrawal behaviour such as absenteeism. As Ahmed (2024) noted, the strength of any profession depends upon the degree of commitment of its members. Teachers' job commitment is conceptualized as being multi-dimensional. Thus, teachers' job commitment is the strength of teachers' identification with and involvement in the school organization. It can be viewed as the dedication that teachers believe or perceive toward particular work and the job they carry out in the school.

All the attractions and attachments of teachers to the work in their school indicated their level of job commitment. Teachers' job commitment refers to the socio-psychological bonding of an individual to his group or organization, its goals and values or to his occupation and profession (Owota & Elliot, 2022). It could manifest in three ways, that is, affective, normative and continuance and each type of commitment ties the individual to the organization in different ways and will differently affect the manner in which the employees conduct themselves in the workplace. Fostering commitment among teachers is important because teachers, who are highly committed stay longer, perform better and actively involved in the work. Commitment in the workplace has the potential to influence organizational effectiveness and efficiency. Ofojebe and Kene-Chiedu (2021) explained job commitment as the strength of the individuals' identification with, involvement in, and commitment to support and attain organizational goals.

Every school has some goals to achieve and for these goals to be successfully achieved, teachers must be committed. Teachers' job commitment is the feeling of dedication among teachers towards their job. This commitment area involves two essential components namely pride in one's being in the teaching job and a strong desire for professional development. In fact after joining the profession they should fully understand as long as they are there, they have to develop pride knowing that this is a noble job charged with great responsibilities as the society hands over its students to this system for their wholesome education. Thahir *et al.* (2022) described job commitment as total organism direction involving not only the conscious mind but the whole direction which is gradually achieved by the individual through a close relationship in which even unconscious tendencies are as much respected as conscious choices. Thahir *et al.* further noted that commitment in job is a state of attachment that defines the relationship between an actor (an individual, a group or organization) and an entity (commitment target).

Fostering the commitment of teachers in public secondary schools is imperative as teachers who are highly committed are likely to stay longer on the job, can perform better than their uncommitted colleagues, and are usually full of excitement to contribute positively to the success of the school. Such teachers will also be ready to go extra mile for the students and the school goals and objectives to be achieved. Some of the factors that may determine the level of

teachers' job commitment in schools include job security, poor conditions of service, the relationship between teachers and students, the quality of the work done by teachers, inadequate teachers' support services, the work environment, availability of resources in schools, prompt payment of salary, and other allowances, adequate incentives among others. The study will be delimited to teachers' support services. To increase the teachers' commitment in the schools with the intention of improving productivity and good behaviour, there is need for principals to encourage and provide good support services for teachers and this might boost their morale for hard work.

Teachers' support services are those services provided to facilitate the implementation of educational policies, attainment of educational goals and promote the effectiveness of the educational system. They are services that can promote teachers' effectiveness in the discharge of their professional responsibilities and also improve students' learning. Egwu *et al.* (2021) described educational support services as those specialized functions that are not typically educational themselves but are aimed at improving teaching and learning in a particular educational system. Therefore, educational support services are provided to help schools to be effective and improve upon teaching and learning. They include all human and other resources that provide support to teachers and learners as well as other aspects of the education system. Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) identified the aims of educational support services to include: to enhance teaching and improve the competence of teachers, provide conducive school environment for learning, make learning experiences realistic and more meaningful to the learners, make education more cost effective and to promote in-service education for teachers.

Support services include those services provided by both professionals and the para-professionals to schools to address diverse learning skills and problems of the students. These services when managed well support the teaching and learning process by addressing the underlying issues such as academic behavioural lapses and mental health problems that challenge and bar effective teaching and learning. Educational support services refer to wide range of services offered to both students and teachers to help them discover their individual academic skills and to become self-sufficient, independent, life-long learners. The personnel who offer these services comprise of a broad range of professionals in guidance/counsellors, facilitators who help teachers develop themselves professionally, librarians, and technicians/technologists (Haryonoa *et al.*, 2020). They work as an integrated team within network of schools, focusing on the provision of group-based and individual support, workforce capacity building and provision of specialized services. Thus, management of educational support services refers to the planning, coordination, direction, channeling and organization of educational resources provided to aid in the smooth running of the school (Zulkiflee *et al.*, 2023). Zulkiflee *et al.* (2023) further noted teachers' support services to include transportation assistance, day care expenses, clothes, vacation benefits, books and supplies, good work environment, academic advising, teamwork, advocacy, course fees, in-service training, license and testing fees or other items that are required for teachers to participate in education. These resources are managed against theft, damage, and sustainability. In this study emphasis was based on three educational support services including: working environment, teachers' in-service training and teamwork.

The work environment is the surroundings in which workers operate. Some of the elements that make up the working environment are obvious, such as the color of the walls and the lighting but others are more abstract, such as the company culture, the relationship with co-

workers and supervisors. It is also an atmosphere that a workplace promotes or affects the staff growth, attitude and mindset. Having a work environment that is positive may help employees feel satisfied at their organisation. Dashwep and Macha (2022) disclosed that organisation can achieve a positive environment by maintaining a healthy school culture, which may include encouraging staff growth, promoting communication and helping staff feel comfortable and safe in the workplace. The most important thing that influences employees' motivation and happiness, and how productive and efficient they can be, all goes down to their working environment. Obi and Akudo (2023) argued that working environment are those workplaces where there is trust, cooperation, safety, risk-taking support, accountability and equity. A healthy workplace environment is ideal when it comes to maintaining a positive outcome in a stressful atmosphere. Thus, a healthy workplace environment improves productivity and reduces costs related to absenteeism, turnover, teachers' compensation and medical claims. When the environment is conducive for teachers, in-service training of teachers becomes vital for improved performance of teachers in schools.

Teachers' in-service training refers to all activities intended to increase the skills and capabilities of teachers. Such programme may include the education provided for employees either in industries, schools or other institutions. Teachers' in-service training is a series of short programmes made available to teachers in order to acquire higher qualification and improve on their professional practices. Therefore, in-service training is an indispensable technique for teachers to be committed to academic duties in the school (Nnorom *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, in-service training gives teachers' opportunities for self-improvement and development to meet the challenges and requirement of new equipment and technologies for performing tasks. Akudo (2023) posited that inadequate provision of in-service training in educational institutions could reduce their enthusiasm in the teaching profession and this could affect their morale, attitude to work, commitment and satisfaction. School administrators are implored to ensure the professional and academic development of staff through meetings, seminars and workshops, building a sense of teamwork to help each staff achieve their potentials, and setting time in staff meeting to discuss professional issues relative to instructional improvement. Thus, in-service training can also improve teachers' teamwork in schools. No wonder, Quines and Nino (2023) identified strong and effective teams as a must have for every organization that seeks the peak of performance abilities. In other words, teamwork has been recognized as the means by which schools strive to achieve the stated goals.

Teamwork is the ability to actively participate in the pursuit of the specific objectives of the organization where performance and a positive attitude is required, and leaders must maintain effective communication and recognize the contributions of team members to achieve the common goal and assume shared responsibilities at a given time. Nwankwo and Ifeanyi (2022) opined that teamwork refers to a group of human beings that have high performance with its members along with the spirit that enables them to achieve the group's goals in the workplace with confidence and cooperation and reduces the workload for everyone, which enables them to exchange ideas. Thus, teamwork practices are an effective leadership behaviour adopted by leaders to bridge the gap between superior subordinate relationship and providing an opportunity for every member of the organization to contribute brains and ingenuity to ensure physical organizational effectiveness. For schools to be successful, everyone must have clear shared goals, a sense of commitment, the ability to work together and other elements of teamwork that support teachers in schools.

Furthermore, teachers whose needs, goals and aspirations are thwarted by the organization, develop feelings of low self-worth, become apathetic, disinterested, frustrated and tend to withhold self-commitment to the work. Thus, the way teacher's support services in public secondary schools are provided and managed might influence teachers' feelings and interest towards their job and commitment to the school. In public secondary schools in Anambra State, it is unfortunate that most secondary school teachers are subjected to work under conditions where there is few or no office facilities; where classrooms are overcrowded with students; where and where there is inadequate provision for support services, they will be less committed and unsatisfied to give their best at work to promote performance as well as enhance moral development of their students. Working under such deplorable conditions, create a negative school climate in which the morale of teachers could be low. This could result in lack of commitment to work among teachers. It is on this background that the researchers sought to determine teachers' support services as predictors of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

It is a reality that teachers are the instrument through which educational objectives can be achieved. If teachers are properly motivated by support services, they might be committed and satisfied to give their best at work to promote performance as well as enhance moral development of their students. This is due to poor teachers' support services prevailing in public secondary schools. The teachers in public secondary schools have to seek for alternative means to make ends meet, causing divided attention, absenteeism from school, irregular attendance to class, lack of concentration, dissatisfaction, low commitment to work among others. These lapses are maybe as a result of poor teachers' support services which is a negative signals coming from the system over low commitment of teachers. This seemed to mean that school management is not working up to expectations. It appears school management does not effectively and efficiently provide support services to teachers in the area of conducive work environment, regular in-service training and building good teamwork among teachers. Against the background that, the researchers sought to determined teachers support services as predictors of their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine teachers' support services as predictors of their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine how:

1. Work environment predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. In-service training predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Teamwork predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does work environment predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

2. What is the predictive value of in-service training on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. How does teamwork predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Work environment does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. In-service training does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Teamwork does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

The design of the study was a correlational research design. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of 6,598 teachers in the 267 public secondary schools from the six education zones in Anambra State was used for the study. The sample of 660 teachers were used for the study. Two instruments were used for data collection: Teachers' Support Services Questionnaire (TSSQ) and Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ). The instruments are structured in three sections namely A, B and C. Section A deals with the personal data of the respondents, while sections B and C dealt with TSSQ and TJCQ.

Teachers' Support Services Questionnaire (TSSQ) as structured by the researcher measured teachers' support services in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument TSSQ contained 30-items spread across three Clusters 'A-C.' Cluster 'A' elicited information on work environment with 10-items; Cluster 'B' elicited information on in-service training with 10-items; and Cluster 'C' elicited information on teamwork with 10-items. These items were placed on 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point). Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJSQ) as structured by the researcher measured job commitment of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The instrument TJCQ has 15-items with a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4 points), Agree (A) (3 points), Disagree (D) (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (SD) (1 point).

The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation. Face validation was done by three experts, two in Educational Management and one in Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The experts were requested to review and critique the various items of the instruments in terms of relevance, clarity, and appropriateness of language and response patterns as they relate to the study. Their criticisms, suggestions and modifications were incorporated into the relevant items to give the instruments their present structure and content. On the other hand, construct validation was carried out with the help SPSS v.25. Construct validity of the instruments for components loading eight factors was explored using Principal Component Analysis approach. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) as a measure of sampling adequacy to conduct the Principal Component Analysis was obtained as 0.891.

The reliability of the instrument was established for the different clusters of the instrument as well as the entire instruments. The reliability was determined by administering copies of the questionnaire to 30 teachers in public secondary schools in Enugu State who were randomly selected in six public secondary schools in Enugu Metropolis. The instruments were administered to the respondents by the researchers with the help of five research assistants. The data collected was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Simple regression analysis was used to answer the research questions and test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

For Regression Coefficient (r)

- + Sign = Positive Prediction
- Sign = Negative Prediction

The negative sign means a negative coefficient which indicates a negative prediction or correlation between variables, while a positive sign means a positive coefficient which indicates a positive prediction or correlation between variables.

For p-value when

- Sig. (2-tailed) < .05: Reject H_0 and Accept H_1
- Sig. (2-tailed) > .05: Do not reject H_0

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of 0.05 the null hypotheses was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: How does work environment predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis with work environment as predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β
Constant	31.124	6.537	
Work Environment	.675	.305	.651
R	.651		
R ²	.592		
Adj. R ²	.546		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 1 indicated that work environment positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.651$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.592 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was highly strong. This implies that 59% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in work environment. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.546 indicating that 55% of the total

variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (work environment). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of work environment is highly strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Again, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.651$) showed that work environment is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that a unit rise in work environment led to 0.651(65%) increase in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of work environment on their job commitment means that teachers' job commitment highly depends on the adequate provision of conducive work environment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the predictive value of in-service training on teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis with in-service training as predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	B	B
Constant	28.163	5.723	
In-Service Training	.582	.294	.578
R	.578		
R^2	.526		
Adj. R^2	.503		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 2 indicated that teachers' in-service training positively predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.578$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.526 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 53% of the variations in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers' in-service training. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.503 indicating that 50% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers' job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers' in-service training). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of in-service training is moderately strong in determining the teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Furthermore, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.578$) showed that teachers' in-service training is a positive predictor of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that an increment in teachers' in-service training led to 0.578(58%) increase in teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers' in-service training on their job commitment means that teachers' job commitment moderately depends on prompt provision of in-service training of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: How does teamwork predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis with teamwork as predictor of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized
	β	β	β
Constant	31.477	6.539	
Teamwork	.582	.342	.567
R	.567		
R ²	.505		
Adj. R ²	.486		

The summary of the simple regression analysis as shown in Table 3 indicated that teachers’ teamwork positively predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as shown by the regression coefficient ($R = 0.567$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.505 indicated that the explanatory power of the variable was moderately strong. This implies that 51% of the variations in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State were accounted for by the variations in teachers’ teamwork. The adjusted R^2 supported the claim of the R^2 with a value of 0.489 indicating that 49% of the total variation in the dependent variable (teachers’ job commitment) was explained by the independent variable (teachers’ teamwork). Thus, adjusted R^2 supports the statement that the explanatory power of teamwork is moderately strong in determining the teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Furthermore, the standardized beta weight ($\beta = 0.567$) showed that teachers’ teamwork is a positive predictor of teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that improvement in teachers’ teamwork led to 0.567(57%) increase in teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Thus, the positive prediction of teachers’ teamwork on their job commitment means that teachers’ job commitment moderately depends on good teamwork of teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₁: Work environment do not significantly predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with work environment do not significantly predict teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized	Std. Dev.	Standardized	t-value	p-value
	β	β	B		
Constant	31.124	6.537		25.941	.000
Work Environment	.675	.305	.651	21.865	.000
R	.651				
R ²	.592				
Adj. R ²	.546				
F	35.734				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 4 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.651 while the R^2 is 0.592 and Adjust R^2 is 0.546. The F-ratio associated with regression is 35.734, the t-test is 21.865 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that work environment does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that work environment significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₂: In-service training does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with in-service training does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	28.163	6.723		26.127	.000
In-Service Training	.582	.294	.578	22.796	.000
R	.578				
R^2	.526				
Adj. R^2	.503				
F	36.119				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 5 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.578 while the R^2 is 0.526 and Adjust R^2 is 0.503. The F-ratio associated with regression is 36.119, the t-test is 22.796 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that in-service training does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that in-service training significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₃: Teamwork does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of significance of simple regression analysis with teamwork does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized β	t- value	p- value
Constant	31.477	6.539		23.928	.000
Teamwork	.582	.342	.567	20.816	.000
R	.567				
R^2	.505				
Adj. R^2	.486				
F	32.397				.000

The summary of the test of significance of simple regression analysis as shown in Table 6 showed that the simple regression coefficient (R) is 0.582 while the R^2 is 0.505 and Adjust R^2 is 0.486. The F-ratio associated with regression is 32.397, the t-test is 20.816 and the P-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than the specified level of significance 0.05, the study therefore rejected the null hypothesis that teamwork does not significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State and accepted the alternative hypothesis that teamwork significantly predicts teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

Findings on how work environment predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that work environment positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This finding is concomitant with that of Dashwep and Macha (2023) that the physical component of the work environment has the strongest effect on the performance and commitment level of teachers in schools. This finding agrees and is related to the findings of Aladetan (2024) that several aspects of work environment which is necessary for human resources management in the school as including creating a positive atmosphere where staff enjoy working and interacting (that is, conducive school climate); providing opportunities for employees' personal growth and development which will push them closer towards achieving both organizational and their own goals. The findings of a related study conducted by Obi and Akudo (2023) confirmed a school environment where teachers are adequately motivated through availability of teaching personnel in order to handle manageable workloads, adequacy of school physical facilities and reward systems, has positive influence on teachers' job satisfaction and commitment which invariably impact on their performances and productivity. More so, good and conducive work environment provide greater physical comfort for teachers and boost their morale.

Findings on how in-service training predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that in-service training positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The reason for this finding might be due to the fact that when teachers are professionally developed, they are likely to be satisfied with and committed to their job. In-service training provides teachers with the opportunity of improving their techniques, skills and methodology as well as equipping them with useful innovative information that can help them function appropriately. In-service training programme creates an avenue for individuals to work as team in solving problems, which are of common concern to all staff as well as contributing to the development of the educational objectives of the school system. So, to encourage growth in performance, other forms of professional development such as workshops, refresher courses, exchanging teaching professional writings and participation in the school programme must be practiced. These will help to complement the already acquired knowledge especially when these processes are brought into reality through the role transition (Nnorom *et al.*, 2022). Akudo (2023) in an earlier study had established that investment in the form of development training was a crucial factor in the development of job commitment for teachers. The result of the study showed that teachers who had low commitment to the profession prior to training became highly committed after they were given opportunity to go for in-service training. Thus, in-service training served to boost teachers' moral and thus, engendered positive work performance and satisfaction among them. This

finding is in consonance with Thahir *et al.* (2022) that, a significant relationship between staff professional development and teachers' job performance in schools. The study is further buttressed by that of the findings of Akuh (2024) who saw in-service training as an aid in fostering personal teaching efficiency which enhances effective classroom strategies and professional competences. Again, Chukwueze (2023) opined that many negative attitudes of personal in the school system can be reduced through in-service training, such negative attitudes include poor work behaviour, how productivity excessive absenteeism, excessive complaints, lack of interest in the job, tiredness and low quality output.

Findings on how teamwork predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State revealed that teamwork positively and significantly predict teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is expected that all things being equal, teachers' job commitment should relate positively and significantly to adequate practices of teachers' teamwork in schools. If teachers have effective teamwork, teachers have a chance to connect with each other too, to share ideas, insights, encouragement and mutual support, which is proven to be more effective than working in isolation from one another, and this has always been a pre-requisite to establishing an effective school community. The finding of the study is in concurrence with the findings of Sunoma *et al.* (2022) that prevailing organisational culture of teamwork to have a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction. They noted that organizational culture such as teamwork, sharing of work difficulties with colleagues, trust, observing one another's teaching. The study in collaboration with Obionu *et al.* (2024a) exhibited a positive and significant relationship which could be as a result of friendly, collaborative, strong bonds of loyalty and tradition in the schools as they have similar features which promote teachers' job commitment in schools. In line with the finding of this study, Nwankwo and Ifeanyi (2022) asserted that intrinsic motivation such as trust, mutual relationship, respect, dignity and investment in workers are collegial relationship in teaching that ensure quality and safety for maintaining the standard of professionalism. It equally brings about the organizational growth and development. In the findings of Quines and Nino (2023), teamwork is achievable through good communication and mutual understanding.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the findings, the study concluded that provision of teachers' support services positively and significantly predicted teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The study recommended that for effective teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State, the state government in collaboration with State education board should continually provide teacher with good support services such that could be so motivating to sustain and increase teachers' work morale efficiency.
2. School management should build a work environment that attracts, retain and motivate teachers so as to help them work comfortable, increase organization productivity and enhance teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Seminars and workshops on effective teamwork practices should be organized by the School Management Boards for teachers from time to time to enhance their job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

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